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Microbial Contamination and Air Quality Assessment of Waste Disposal Equipment and Personnel in Benin City, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Poor waste management practices and occupational safety measures in developing countries such as Nigeria, presents significant environmental and public health concerns. The study assessed the microbial and air quality of waste disposal equipment and personnel in Benin City, Nigeria. Data were collected from three refuse collection sites (A, B,C) in Benin City. Microbial air sampling were conducted using the settle plate technique. Standard analytical methods were used to characterize the isolates. The results showed airborne microbial load varied between $4.0 \times 10^2 \pm 2.55$ and $9.0 \times 10^2 \pm 2.16$ CFU/m³ for bacteria and $4.67 \times 10^2 \pm 1.25$ to $5.3 \times 10^2 \pm 2.49$ CFU/m³ for fungi. In contrast, truck interior surfaces showed markedly elevated loads ($5.5 \times 10^3 \pm 0.5$ – $6.7 \times 10^3 \pm 4.59$ CFU/g bacteria; $7.5 \times 10^3 \pm 1.5$ – $9.67 \times 10^3 \pm 0.47$ CFU/g fungi). Skin samples showed higher fungal than bacterial loads, particularly at Sites A and B ($5.50 \times 10^3 \pm 0.5$ CFU each). Sputum samples exhibited elevated bacterial and fungal counts, with Site B workers showing the highest bacterial load ($4.77 \times 10^3 \pm 2.3$ CFU), while Site C had the highest fungal load ($4.47 \times 10^3 \pm 1.12$ CFU). Microbial analysis identified the presence of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Mucor* species. The Multiple Antibiotic Resistance (MAR) indices indicated high risk resistance of *S.aureus* and moderate resistance among the isolates. Air quality assessment showed elevated concentrations of particulate matter and bioaerosols. The refuse workers are at risk of possible infections, underscoring the need for enhanced occupational health interventions. These findings highlighted the critical importance of proper waste management procedures, regular sanitation, and consistent use of personal protective equipment to reduce exposure risks among waste handlers

Keywords: Waste, Microbial load, Air quality, Bioaerosols, Collection sites, Refuse workers.

INTRODUCTION

Effective waste management involves the systematic coordination of waste collection, transit, treatment, and disposal to mitigate hazardous impacts on environmental aesthetics, public health, and ecological sustainability (Binion & Gutberlet, 2012). However, routine waste handling and sorting operations often release accumulated biological agents into the atmosphere. These waste-borne microorganisms become aerosolized as bioaerosols, which are readily inhaled by personnel working within these environments. Prolonged occupational exposure to these airborne bacteria, fungi, and their associated toxins such as

endotoxins and mycotoxins is linked to diverse medical complications, primarily marked by severe shifts in systemic inflammatory biomarkers (Eriksen *et al.*, 2023; Madsen *et al.*, 2020; Rasmussen *et al.*, 2023). These include acute respiratory disorders, diminished pulmonary function, gastrointestinal distress, and dermal or ocular irritation (Eriksen *et al.*, 2023; Samadi *et al.*, 2024).

In rapidly urbanizing centess across developing nations like Nigeria, municipal solid waste management presents escalating challenges (Binion & Gutberlet, 2012). In Benin City, waste collection frequently involves the manual handling of mixed, unsorted household refuse, exposing workers to severe occupational hazards. Waste generated by households, markets, schools, small scale industries, etc. in suburban communities are usually transported using garbage trucks to landfill or open dumpsites. Beyond musculoskeletal strain, physical injuries, and psychological fatigue driven by strenuous working conditions ((Ferronato & Torretta, 2019; Obueh *et al.*, 2024; Madsen *et al.*, 2020), manifold disease infestation could lead to major health and environmental problems because the laborers face heightened susceptibility to microbial attacks. This vulnerability is exacerbated by evolving municipal waste dynamics, prolonged shifts, a lack of institutional training, and the systemic absence of personal protective equipment (Mmereki *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, the confined and poorly ventilated microenvironments of refuse trucks accumulate higher concentrations of biological contaminants compared to open-air dumpsites, intensifying the risk to both workers and proximate communities (Madsen *et al.*, 2016; Eriksen *et al.*, 2023; Rasmussen *et al.*, 2023).

Refuse trucks serve as central mobile reservoirs and vectors for pathogenic bacteria, fungi, and viruses derived from decomposing organic matter and co-mingled hazardous wastes (Madsen *et al.*, 2016).. The decomposition of organic fractions within enclosed truck compartments generates toxic gaseous emissions and bioaerosols that degrade ambient air quality and trigger respiratory illnesses. Refuse workers encounter these biological contaminants not only during external manual loading but also within the vehicle cabins. Recent toxicological testing confirms that cabin air filters often track critical accumulations of cytotoxic *Aspergillus*, *E. coli*, and endotoxins that continuously resuspend into the breathing zone (Gołofit-Szymczak *et al.*, 2023). Internal exposure occurs when settled particulate matter becomes resuspended by vehicular movement or is circulated through the truck's ventilation systems (Gołofit-Szymczak *et al.*, 2023), increasing inhalation exposure among both drivers and loaders (Rasmussen *et al.*, 2023).

Epidemiological data confirms that waste management personnel are routinely exposed to critical thresholds of biological pollutants, resulting in chronic coughs, nasal inflammation, and dermatological infections (Poole & Basu, 2017; Eriksen *et al.*, 2023). While waste handling in developed nations is largely mechanized and regulated by stringent statutory safety frameworks and mandatory personal protective equipment compliance, operations in developing countries remain heavily reliant on manual labor. Consequently, workers frequently handle decomposing biomass, animal carcasses, and faecal matter without technological or sanitary barriers, driving up the incidence of both communicable and non-communicable occupational diseases (Madsen *et al.*, 2020).

In Benin City, waste transit occurs under substandard occupational and sanitary conditions. When refuse collection vehicles are not routinely washed and chemically disinfected, they turn into active breeding grounds for pathogens. During collection cycles, workers positioned at the rear of the vehicles are directly exposed to plumes of bioaerosols generated by waste compaction and loading. These airborne microbes routinely migrate into the driver's cabin, and workers often inadvertently cross-contaminate indoor environments via their soiled clothing (Madsen *et al.*, 2016).

Despite these severe, escalating public health risks, there is a critical dearth of empirical data regarding the exact microbial loads, vehicular air quality, and corresponding health profiles of refuse workers in Benin City. This data gap limits evidence-based policy-making and occupational health interventions. Addressing this gap is essential for understanding exposure pathways and improving worker safety standards. Accordingly, this study evaluated the microbial status and air quality of municipal refuse trucks, while concurrently analyzing clinical samples from waste disposal workers within Benin City to identify occupational health risks.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Location and Sample Collection

The study was conducted across three municipal waste disposal companies in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria, designated as Site A, Site B, and Site C. One refuse truck was sampled per company. Clinical specimens, ambient air samples, and physical swabs were systematically collected from each site.

Air Sampling

A total of nine air samples were collected using the settle plate technique. Nutrient Agar (NA) and MacConkey Agar (MCA) plates were used for bacterial isolation, while Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) was used for fungi as was employed by CLSI (2024) in an earlier study. The plates were exposed on a platform within each truck's dump compartment for 15 minutes, secured in a sterile cooler, and transported to the laboratory.

Sputum Collection

Nine sputum specimens were obtained from nine waste disposal workers (three collectors per company). Collectors were provided with sterile, labeled containers and instructed on proper expectoration techniques. Samples were preserved in a cooling box during transit.

Skin and Surface Swabbing

Nine skin swab samples as was recommended by CLSI (2024), were collected from the hands and skin of the same nine workers (three per company) using sterile swab sticks pre-moistened with peptone water. Concurrently, swab samples were gathered from the dump compartments and cabin seating areas of each vehicle. All swabs were stored in a cooled container for transport.

Physicochemical Air Quality Assessment

Air quality profiling inside the truck compartments was performed using a calibrated Narootte (Model 5V DC) air quality monitoring device. As earlier recommended by Ibid (2024), the detector was placed on a platform within each compartment for 5 minutes and the respective parameters monitored in triplicate included: total volatile organic compounds (TVOCs), formaldehyde (HCHO), particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) and (PM₁₀), carbon monoxide (CO), and carbon dioxide (CO₂).

Microbiological Enumeration

Sputum samples were serially diluted. Ten milliliter of sterile distilled water was thoroughly mixed with each specimen to create a stock solution. Stepwise serial dilutions were prepared in test tubes containing 9 mL of sterile distilled water (Ibid, 2024). In their description, one mL of the inoculums was inoculated onto prepared media and incubated at 36°C for 24 hours. Swab containers were reconstituted with 3 mL of sterile distilled water, inoculated onto agar surfaces, and incubated at 36°C for 24 hours.

Exposed air sampling plates were incubated to determine microbial loads. Bacterial plates (NA and MCA) were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours to record colony-forming units. Fungal plates (PDA) were incubated at 37°C for 48 hours to evaluate fungal load.

Identification of Isolates

Pure cultures were obtained via repeated sub-culturing. Fungal isolates were identified macroscopically (colony colour, texture, growth pattern) and microscopically. The colonies were purified on a fresh agar, and subsequently identified. The identification of the isolates was by using Bergey's Manual of Systemic Bacteriology (Ibid, 2024).

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (AST)

AST was conducted using the Kirby-Bauer agar disc diffusion method on Mueller-Hinton Agar (Ibid, 2024). In which process, sterilized media (autoclaved at 121°C for 25 minutes) was poured into Petri dishes. Organisms were lawn-inoculated uniformly across the agar using sterile swabs, and commercial antibiotic discs were placed on the surface. Following incubation at 37°C for 24 hours, zones of inhibition were measured in millimetres using a metric rule. Results were interpreted as sensitive, intermediate, or resistant based on the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute guidelines (Ibid, 2024).

Multiple Antibiotic Resistance (MAR) Indexing

The MAR index was calculated to evaluate the multidrug resistance profile of each bacterial isolate using the following formula: The formula used for the calculation are expressed as:

MAR Index = Number of antibiotics to which the isolate is resistant/ Total number of antibiotics tested (Ibid, 2024)

A higher MAR index value suggests a greater level of resistance among the bacterial isolates.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were calculated to summarize the data obtained from microbial counts and air quality parameters. The mean was used to determine the average value of observations, while the standard deviation was used to measure the degree of dispersion of values around the mean.

RESULTS

Table 1: Microbial Counts across Collection Sites from Refuse Trucks and Surroundings

Sample Type	Site	Mean Bacterial Count	Mean Fungal Count
Air sample (CFU/m ³)	A	$9.0 \times 10^2 \pm 2.16$	$5.0 \times 10^2 \pm 0.816$
	B	$4.0 \times 10^2 \pm 2.55$	$5.3 \times 10^2 \pm 2.49$
	C	$6.67 \times 10^2 \pm 1.69$	$4.67 \times 10^2 \pm 1.25$
Truck interior swab (CFU/ cm ²)	A	$6.5 \times 10^3 \pm 0.5$	$8.5 \times 10^3 \pm 0.5$
	B	$5.5 \times 10^3 \pm 0.5$	$9.67 \times 10^3 \pm 0.47$
	C	$6.7 \times 10^3 \pm 4.59$	$7.5 \times 10^3 \pm 1.5$
Waste dump swab (CFU/ cm ²)	A	$7.0 \times 10^3 \pm 1.0$	$8.0 \times 10^3 \pm 0.82$
	B	$3.8 \times 10^3 \pm 3.2$	$5.0 \times 10^3 \pm 0.72$
	C	$7.0 \times 10^3 \pm 4.2$	$7.5 \times 10^3 \pm 1.5$

Table 2. Microbial Counts of Clinical Samples (Skin and Sputum) of Refuse Disposal Workers by Site

Sample	Site A	Site B	Site C
Skin – Bacterial (CFU/cm ²)	$4.56 \times 10^3 \pm 1.12$	$4.83 \times 10^3 \pm 2.5$	$2.83 \times 10^3 \pm 1.09$
Skin –Fungal (CFU/ cm ²)	$5.50 \times 10^3 \pm 0.5$	$5.50 \times 10^3 \pm 0.5$	$4.33 \times 10^3 \pm 2.9$
Sputum–Bacterial (CFU/ml)	$3.57 \times 10^3 \pm 2.5$	$4.77 \times 10^3 \pm 2.3$	$4.70 \times 10^3 \pm 2.1$
Sputum–Fungal (CFU/ml)	$3.35 \times 10^3 \pm 1.1$	$3.70 \times 10^3 \pm 1.7$	$4.47 \times 10^3 \pm 1.12$

Table 3: Identified Bacterial and Fungal Isolates from Air Sample of Waste Trucks

Collection Truck Site	Bacterial isolates	Fungal isolates
A	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>
B	<i>Escherichia coli, Micrococcus sp.</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>
C	<i>Moraxella osloensis, Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Mucor sp.</i>

Table 4: Identified Bacterial Isolates from Swab Samples of Waste Disposal Trucks

Collection Site	Probable isolates
A	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
B	<i>Escherichia coli</i> <i>Bacillus subtilis</i>
C	<i>Acinetobacter</i> sp. <i>Klebsiella aerogenes</i> <i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i>

Table 5: Identified Bacterial Isolates from Sputum Samples of Waste Collectors

Collection Site	Waste Collector	Probable isolate
A	1	<i>Yersinia pestis</i>
	2	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
	3	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
B	1	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
	2	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>
	3	<i>Moraxella catarrhalis</i>
C	1	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>
	2	<i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i>
	3	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>

Table 6: Identified Bacterial Isolates from Skin Swab Samples of Waste Collectors

Collection Site	Waste Collector	Probable isolate
A	1	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
	2	<i>Klebsiella aerogenes</i>
	3	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
B	1	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>
	2	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>
	3	<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>
C	1	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
	2	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>
	3	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>

Table 7. Air Quality Parameters Measured with Reference Limits

Parameter	Unit	Site A	Site B	Site C	WHO/Ref Limit (2021)	Status
Formaldehyde (HCHO)	mg/m ³	1.999	1.999	1.999	0.1	Very high
Total Volatile Organic Compounds (TVOC)	mg/m ³	1.999	1.999	1.891	0.30	Very high
Particulate Matter (PM _{2.5})	µg/m ³	13	32	35	15	B–C exceed

Particulate Matter (PM ₁₀)	µg/m ³	16	33	25	45	Within limit
Carbon Monoxide (CO)	ppm	0.41	0.69	0.41	10	Within
Carbon Dioxide (CO ₂)	ppm	4595	5000	4991	500–1000	Extreme

Table 8: Air Quality Parameter Exceedance Index Relative to WHO Standards and Associated Health Risk Categories

Parameter	WHO Limit	Mean Value	% Exceedance	Health Risk
Formaldehyde (HCHO)(mg/m ³)	0.10	1.999	1899 ↑	Severe
Total Volatile Organic Compounds (TVOC)(mg/m ³)	0.30	1.963	554 ↑	Severe
Particulate Matter (PM _{2.5})µg/m ³	15	26.7	78 ↑	Unhealthy
Particulate Matter (PM ₁₀)µg/m ³	45	24.7	–	Moderate
Carbon Monoxide (CO) ppm	10	0.50	–	Safe
Carbon Dioxide (CO ₂) ppm	500	4862	872 ↑	Extreme

Table 9: Pattern of Antibiotic Susceptibility in Gram-positive Bacterial Isolates

Bacterial Isolate	CXM	PEF	CRO	AZM	OFL	CIP	GEM	LUX	MAR Index
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	9(R)	11(R)	0(R)	7(R)	10(R)	5(R)	9(R)	12(R)	1
<i>Micrococcus sp.</i>	9(R)	20(S)	12(I)	15(I)	13(I)	19(S)	12(I)	20(S)	0.125
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	10(R)	20(S)	5(R)	20(S)	20(S)	20(S)	19(S)	20(S)	0.25
<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	15(I)	20(S)	15(I)	20(S)	20(S)	20(S)	20(S)	20(S)	0

Key:

xm=Cefuroxime(30µg),Pef=Pefloxacin(5µg),Cro=Ceftraixone(5µg),Azm=Arithromycin(15µg),OfI=Ofloxacin(5µg),Cip=Ciprofl oxacin(5µg),Gen=Gentamicin(10µg),Luv=Levofloxacin(5µg) R indicates Resistance ≤13 , I=Intermediate ≤16, S= Susceptible ≥17

NOTE: MAR Index ≥0.5 indicates high multiple antibiotics resistance, <0.2 indicates low multiple antibiotics resistance

Table 10: Pattern of Antibiotic Susceptibility in Gram-negative Bacterial Isolates

Bacterial isolates	CAZ	LUX	GEN	CIP	OFL	NIT	CRO	AUG	MAR Index
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	15(I)	20(S)	15(I)	20(S)	18(S)	0(R)	0(R)	0(R)	0.375
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	0(R)	19(S)	10(R)	20(S)	14(I)	0(R)	6(R)	0(R)	0.125
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	13(R)	20(S)	20(S)	20(S)	20(S)	6(R)	0(R)	5(R)	0.25
<i>Moraxella osloensis</i>	14(I)	20(S)	20(S)	20(S)	20(S)	0(R)	4(R)	6(R)	0.375
<i>Acinetobacter sp.</i>	19(S)	20(S)	19(S)	20(S)	20(S)	14(I)	6(R)	4(R)	0.125
<i>Klebsiella aerogenes</i>	12(I)	20(S)	18(S)	19(S)	20(S)	0(R)	0(R)	0(R)	0.375

KEY:

Caz=Ceftazidime(30µg),Luv=Levofloxacin(5µg),Gen=Gentamicin(10µg),Cip=Ciprofloxacin(5µg),OfI=Ofloxacin(5µg),Nit=Nitrofurantoin(30µg),Cro=Ceftraixone(30µg),Aug=Augmentin (30µg)

R Indicates Resistance ≤13 , I=Intermediate ≤16, S= Susceptible ≥17

Note: Multiple antibiotic resistance (mar) index ≥0.5 indicates high multiple antibiotics resistance, <0.2 indicates low multiple antibiotics resistance

Microbiological and air quality assessments across the study sites revealed substantial microbial and bioaerosol burdens linked to waste-handling operations. The significantly elevated bacterial load observed at Site A indicates that waste handling environments serve as active zones for microbial proliferation and worker exposure. This finding aligned with established literature showing that municipal waste sites inherently generate high volumes of airborne microorganisms through the rapid decomposition of organic materials and the continuous mechanical agitation of waste during collection and compaction (Duquenne, *et al.*, 2024).

While bacterial distribution varied across the collection zones, airborne fungal counts were moderately comparable across all monitored locations. Notably, Site B recorded the maximum fungal concentration of 5.3×10^2 CFU/m³. Fungi are highly efficient colonizers of decaying organic matter; their elevated presence around waste transport vehicles reinforces the fact that municipal refuse handling generates highly mobile bioaerosols capable of widespread environmental dispersion.

The viable bacterial aerosol concentrations quantified near active operations reached peak levels of $10,353 \pm 3,701$ CFU/m³. This substantial exposure profile confirms that bioaerosol concentrations are highly dynamic, fluctuating based on the specific work activity, immediate proximity to the refuse source, and prevailing local environmental conditions (Zliang *et al.*, 2023).

The resulting bacteria-to-fungi ratios offer deeper insights into the ecological dominance of specific microbial groups and the exact environmental pressures driving them. In direct air samples, the marked dominance of bacteria indicates rapid, active aerosolization caused by the physical disturbance of fresh waste and intensive human-waste interactions. This structural pattern mirrors trends documented in global municipal waste settings, where initial bacterial dominance is fueled by the mechanical breakdown of organic substrates and the continuous resuspension of contaminated particulate matter (Duquenne, *et al.*, 2024).

Conversely, the prominent fungal loads observed across specific sampling locations are heavily driven by elevated microclimatic moisture and prolonged organic decomposition, which create an ideal substrate for fungal vegetative growth and subsequent sporulation (Kontro *et al.*, 2022). Refuse trucks systematically create enclosed, highly humid microenvironments that actively promote fungal accumulation, particularly when organic waste residues and moisture are allowed to remain within the vehicle compartments. This microclimatic effect is well-documented; enclosed waste sorting and transport environments with limited ventilation routinely exhibit massive fungal spore accumulation (Duquenne *et al.*, 2024).

The capacity of fungi to thrive in these conditions is further supported by the positive correlation observed in this study between relative humidity and airborne fungal concentrations, confirming that ambient moisture levels dictate fungal proliferation rates (Duquenne *et al.*, 2024; Kontro *et al.*, 2022). Ultimately, while landfill and open waste-processing sites typically exhibit higher overall bacterial abundance due to nutrient-rich organic substrates and mechanical disturbances (Kontro *et al.*, 2022; Pascale *et al.*, 2022), the enclosed structure of refuse trucks introduces a distinct humid environment that accelerates fungal risks.

Evaluating the cumulative environmental burden combining both bacterial and fungal counts is a critical metric for assessing baseline occupational hygiene, public health risks, and ambient environmental quality. Although Site C exhibited the highest distinct bacterial load, Site A presented a more severe cumulative hazard due to its disproportionately large fungal contribution. Recent architectural and environmental microbiology studies indicate that while airborne bacterial populations are primarily introduced into indoor or semi-enclosed spaces by human occupants via skin, oral, and gut microbiomes, fungal populations are tied directly to microclimatic conditions, ventilation failures, and the presence of damp, organic, or porous materials (Kontro *et al.*, 2022).

The relative uniformity between the bacterial and fungal loads at Site A indicates an operational environment characterized by both heavy human occupancy/handling intensity and severe structural dampness within the waste matrix. High cumulative microbial loads serve as a direct, quantifiable proxy for localized infection risks. For context, clinical and occupational health assessments show that elevated colony-forming units (CFUs) on surfaces and in the immediate breathing zone are statistically correlated

with heightened rates of infection transmission (Eduard, 2009). Because the combined microbial loads at both Site A and Site C exceeded a critical threshold of 3.7×10^4 CFU, these specific operational zones require significantly more aggressive, firm chemical disinfection protocols than the relatively lower-load environment of Site B.

The spatial variances observed between Site C (characterized by high bacterial counts) and Site B (characterized by high fungal dominance) strongly corroborate built-environment models established by (Kelley & Gilbert, 2013). These models state that bacterial density is tightly linked to direct human occupancy and operational contact, whereas fungal dominance signals a deeply embedded environmental or structural source, such as impacted organic debris. Fungi act as highly resilient opportunistic pathogens, expanding rapidly when ambient dust levels rise or when confined spaces lack proper air exchange, allowing them to proliferate even when bacterial competition is low ((Eduard, 2009).

The distinct microbial burdens quantified on the skin and within the sputum samples of the refuse workers provide clear evidence of intense occupational exposure and direct biological colonization. Dermal swab analysis revealed that Site B workers suffered the highest bacterial loads, while workers at both Site A and Site B shared the highest fungal burdens. This severe dermal contamination indicates that workers operating at these specific sites face an elevated risk of contracting occupational dermatosis and secondary skin infections.

Analysis of respiratory sputum samples revealed an equally hazardous exposure pathway: Site C workers showed the highest respiratory fungal colonization, while Site B workers led in bacterial sputum loads. This confirms the immediate inhalation of bioaerosols; workers are actively inhaling contaminated dust and biological particles that systematically settle along the upper and lower respiratory tracts.

These microbiological findings are heavily validated by epidemiological data from Lavoie *et al.* (2006), who documented that 87% of waste management workers surveyed reported chronic skin complaints, while 57% suffered from persistent respiratory issues. The isolation of predominant pathogens such as *Staphylococcus aureus* on the skin and *Candida* species within the respiratory tract underscores that the manual, "artisanal" nature of waste collection in Benin City serves as the primary driver for these dangerously high microbial counts.

Furthermore, the observation of overlapping microbial species profiles on the workers' skin and within their sputum samples mirror the occupational exposure models of Madsen *et al.* (2020), who identified over 150 matching bacterial species across workers' hands and immediate inhalation zones (Lavoie *et al.*, 2006; Eduard, 2009). This structural overlap proves that poor hand-to-mouth hygiene, inadequate field sanitation, and unmitigated airborne dust work synergistically to multiply the total biological and systemic burden borne by these municipal workers.

Ambient air quality monitoring across the three outdoor stations (Sites A, B, and C) at the waste dump site revealed severe environmental contamination driven by open-air waste decomposition and heavy diesel truck traffic. Formaldehyde (HCHO) and Total Volatile Organic Compounds (TVOC) both exhibited critical breaches of international safety standards, with HCHO consistently reaching 1.999 mg/m^3 (a 1,899% exceedance) and TVOC averaging 1.963 mg/m^3 (a 554% exceedance). These extreme values represent a severe health risk, originating from the volatilization of unmanaged chemical waste and the continuous release of unburnt hydrocarbons from idling and operating waste-collection trucks. Furthermore, ambient Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) concentrations were highly anomalous, averaging 4,862 ppm and peaking at 5,000 ppm at Site B. This Extreme 872% breach of standard ambient baselines indicates a heavy atmospheric loading of landfill gas generated via anaerobic waste decay, coupled with concentrated, low-lying heavy vehicle exhaust plumes trapped in the immediate microenvironment.

Suspended particulate matter profiles highlight a localized, transport-driven dispersion pattern across the dump site. Fine respirable particles (PM_{2.5}) averaged $26.7 \text{ } \mu\text{g/m}^3$, marking an unhealthy 78% exceedance of the $15 \text{ } \mu\text{g/m}^3$ WHO limit. The data shows distinct spatial variations, where Site A ($13 \text{ } \mu\text{g/m}^3$) remained safe, but Sites B ($32 \text{ } \mu\text{g/m}^3$) and C ($35 \text{ } \mu\text{g/m}^3$) suffered heavy contamination. This spike is directly attributed to outdoor operational zones characterized by intense truck movements, mechanical waste tipping, and windblown ash or soot. Conversely, coarse dust (PM₁₀) remained within the $45 \text{ } \mu\text{g/m}^3$ reference limit at all stations with a mean of $24.7 \text{ } \mu\text{g/m}^3$ (Moderate risk), while Carbon Monoxide (CO)

also stabilized safely under the threshold at 0.50 ppm. This localized equilibrium indicates that the ambient atmospheric threat at this facility is primarily driven by fine diesel soot, gaseous combustion byproducts, and toxic organic vapors rather than macro-level fugitive dust.

The antibiotic susceptibility profiles of the isolated Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria demonstrate varying degrees of resistance, with *Staphylococcus aureus* emerging as the most critical public health concern. Among the Gram-positive isolates, *S. aureus* exhibited absolute resistance to all eight tested antibiotics, including beta-lactams (cefuroxime, ceftriaxone) and fluoroquinolones (ciprofloxacin, levofloxacin), yielding a maximum Multiple Antibiotic Resistance (MAR) index of 1.0. This extreme multi-drug resistance profile underscores a Severe therapeutic challenge, especially since these bacteria were isolated from a waste dump environment where selective pressure from discarded pharmaceuticals is high. Conversely, other Gram-positive isolates like *Micrococcus sp.*, *Bacillus subtilis*, and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* remained largely manageable, showing low MAR indices (<0.25) and maintaining high susceptibility to broad-spectrum fluoroquinolones like pefloxacin and levofloxacin. The isolation of these bacterial species from the dumpsites is in agreement with the studies Obueh *et al.* (2024). They showed that the resistance demonstrated by these bacterial isolates against the antibiotics could be attributed to the production of enzymes, which inactivate or modify antibiotics.

The Gram-negative isolates displayed a more uniform, moderate pattern of multi-drug resistance, heavily driven by widespread insensitivity to specific legacy antibiotics. All six Gram-negative species including *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Klebsiella pneumonia* exhibited complete or near-complete resistance to nitrofurantoin, Ceftriaxone, and Augmentin (amoxicillin/clavulanic acid). This widespread beta-lactam and nitrofurantoin resistance resulted in elevated MAR indices ranging from 0.125 to 0.375, placing several isolates just below the high-risk 0.5 threshold. Despite these concerning resistance pockets, fluoroquinolones specifically levofloxacin and ciprofloxacin maintained excellent therapeutic efficacy, achieving maximum zone diameters of 19–20 mm (Susceptible) across all Gram-negative isolates. This structural dichotomy in the data suggests that while plasmid-mediated resistance to common beta-lactams is heavily circulating within the dump site ecosystem, advanced fluoroquinolones remain highly viable frontline agents for environmental pathogen control.

CONCLUSION

This integrated environmental and microbiological assessment demonstrates that municipal waste dump sites and truck operations generate severe, multi-pathway public health risks. The concurrent escalation of outdoor volatile organic compounds (Formaldehyde and TVOC), respirable fine particulates ($\{PM\ 2.5\}$), and biogenic gases (CO_2) forms a highly hazardous ambient envelope. When coupled with peak viable bioaerosol concentrations exceeding 1.0×10^4 CFU/m³, this microenvironment induces heavy dermal and upper-respiratory colonization among the workforce. Furthermore, the environmental selection pressure within this dump site matrix has catalyzed a critical public health threat, as evidenced by the extreme multidrug resistance profile of *Staphylococcus aureus* (MAR Index = 1.0) and widespread beta-lactam resistance among Gram-negative isolates like *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. While legacy antibiotics are rapidly losing efficacy due to heavy selective pressures within the waste matrix, advanced fluoroquinolones (levofloxacin and ciprofloxacin) remain highly viable.

Ultimately, the spatial heterogeneity of these pollutants indicates that while mechanical dumping drives fine particulate and bacterial dissemination, vehicular confinement and stagnant airspace accelerate fungal and chemical exhaust gas hazards. Enforcing strict compliance with heavy-duty respiratory masks, protective gloves, and body coverings to prevent bioaerosol inhalation and dermal contact, Implement mandatory, daily chemical disinfection for refuse truck compartments and high-load sites (Sites A and C) to suppress microbial reservoirs, Redesign waste truck compartments to improve ventilation and reduce internal humidity, preventing fungal sporulation, establish mandatory workplace hand-washing stations and deliver regular occupational hygiene training to eliminate hand-to-mouth microbial transfer and implement routine bioaerosol and air quality surveillance across waste-handling sites to dynamically track exposure risks are highly recommended

REFERENCES

- Binion, E., and Gutberlet, J. (2012). The effects of handling solid waste on the wellbeing of informal and organized recyclers: A review of the literature. *International Journal of Occupational and Environmental Health*, 18(1), 43–52. <https://doi.org/10.1179/1077352512Z.0000000001>
- Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) (2024) *Performance Standards for Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing*. 34th Edition, CLSI, M100
- Duquenne, P., Simon, X., Coulais, C., Koehler, V., Degois, J., and Facon, B. (2024). Bioaerosol exposure during sorting of municipal solid, commercial and industrial waste: Concentration levels, size distribution, and biodiversity of airborne fungal. *Atmosphere*, 15(4), 461. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos15040461>
- Eduard, W. (2009). Fungal spores: A critical review of occupational exposure and health effects. *Critical Reviews in Toxicology*, 39(10), 799–864. <https://doi.org/10.3109/10408440903307333>
- Eriksen, E., Afanou, A. K., Madsen, A. M., Straumfors, A., Eiler, A., and Graff, P. (2023). Occupational exposure to inhalable pathogenic microorganisms in waste sorting. *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health*, 253, 114240. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2023.114240>
- Ferronato, N., and Torretta, V. (2019). Waste mismanagement in developing countries: A review of global issues. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(6), 1060. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16061060>
- Gołofit-Szymczak, M., Wójcik-Fatla, A., Stobnicka-Kupiec, A., and Górný, R. L. (2023). Filters of automobile air conditioning systems as an in-car source of exposure to infections and toxic moulds. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 30(49), 108188–108200. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-29947-y>
- Kelley, S. T., and Gilbert, J. A. (2013). Studying the microbiology of the indoor environment. *Science*, 342(6158), 1057–1058. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1244698>
- Kontro, M. H., Kirsi, M., and Laitinen, S. K. (2022). Exposure to bacterial and fungal bioaerosols in facilities processing biodegradable waste. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10, 789861. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.789861>
- Lavoie, J., Dunkerley, C. J., Kosatsky, T., and Dufresne, A. (2006). Exposure to aerosolized bacteria and fungi among workers in a municipal solid waste recycling facility. *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Hygiene*, 3(12), 653–667. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15459620600918924>
- Madsen, A. M., Alwan, T., Ørberg, A., Uhrbrand, K., and Jørgensen, M. B. (2016). Waste workers' exposure to airborne fungal and bacterial species in the truck cab and during waste collection. *Annals of Work Exposures and Health*, 60(6), 651–668. <https://doi.org/10.1093/annhyg/mew021>
- Madsen, A. M., Frederiksen, M. W., Bjerregaard, M., and Tendal, K. (2020). Measures to reduce the exposure of waste collection workers to hand borne and airborne microorganisms and inflammogenic dust. *Waste Management*, 101, 241–249. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2019.10.023>
- Mmereki, D., Baldwin, A., Li, B., and Liu, M. (2016). Healthcare waste management in developing countries: A review. *Journal of Environmental and Public Health*, 2016, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/9812423>
- Obueh H.O., Maduka N., Egharevba-Ojo , P.A., Enerijiofi K.E., Ikhazuangbe-Benson C (2024). Effect of Dumpsite Waste on Soil, Drinking Water Sources, and Antibiotic Susceptibility of Isolates, in a Sub-urban Community, Benin City, Nigeria. *Science World Journal* 19(3), 625 - 633. <https://dx.doi.org/10.4314/swj.v19i3.6>
- Pascale, E., Franchitti, E., Zanchi, N., Anedda, E., Bonetta, S., and Traversi, D. (2022). Bioaerosol indicators in waste and composting plants. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 10, 777598. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2022.777598>
- Poole, C. J. M., and Basu, S. (2017). Occupational illness in the waste and recycling sector: A systematic review. *Occupational Medicine*, 67(8), 626–636. <https://doi.org/10.1093/occmed/kqx153>

- Rasmussen, P. U., Frederiksen, M. W., Carøe, T. K., and Madsen, A. M. (2023). Health symptoms, inflammation, and bioaerosol exposure in workers at biowaste pretreatment plants. *Waste Management*, 167, 173–182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2023.05.042>
- Samadi, S., Wouters, I. M., Houbraken, J., Jamshidifard, A. R., Van Eerdenburg, F., and Heederik, D. J. J. (2019). Exposure to inhalable dust, endotoxins, and bioaerosols in waste sorting plants and association with inflammatory biomarkers. *Science of the Total Environment*, 671, 224–233.
- Zhang, T., et al. (2023). Distribution characteristics and potential risks of bacterial aerosol in waste transfer station. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 326, 116599. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.116599>